

THE USAGE OF LANGUAGE PHENOMENA IN THE TRANSFER OF THOUGHT TO SPEECH

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of language phenomena in transferring thought into speech. Analysis of language phenomena can be studied in the syntactic stylistics department of linguistics. Syntax deals with the arrangement of words, determining the position of words in the fluency of speech, and forms linguistic phenomena for the correct construction of sentences. Sometimes there is a need to amplify speech, and normative devices are traditionally involved in speech. Examples of such devices are known and they are systematized according to certain principles. It is in this sense that the article talks about how linguistic events and devices are necessary to enrich our speech and express our thoughts fluently. Several linguistic phenomena and their classification are mentioned in the article. The need for a detailed study of language phenomena based on scientific and theoretical sources by itself causes an increase in research on this topic, and the program of our article serves as a basis for this research.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada fikrni nutqga ko'chirishda til hodisalarinig o'rni haqida fikr yuritilgan. Til hodisalarining tahlili bilan tilshunoslikning sintaktik stilistika bo'limida o'rganish mumkin. Sintaksis so'zlarni joylashtirish, nutqni ravon qilishda so'zning o'rnini belgilab berish bilan shug'ullanadi va jummalarni to'g'ri qurish uchun til hodisalarini shakllantiradi. Ba'zan nutqni kuchaytirish zarurati tug'iladi va me'yoriy qurilmalar an'anaviy ravishda nutqda ishtirok etadi. Bunday qurilmalarning namunalari ma'lum va ular ba'zi prinsiplarga muvofiq tizimlashtirilgan. Aynan shu jihatdan maqolada lisoniy hodisalar va qurilmalarning nutqimizni boyitish va fikrimizni ravon qilishimiz uchun nechog'lik zarurligi haqida gap boradi. Maqolada bir nechta til hodisalari va ularning tasnifi aytib o'tilgan. Til hodisalarini ilmiy-nazariy manbalar asosida atroflicha o'rganishga bo'lgan ehtiyoj o'z-o'zidan bu mavzuga taaluqli tadqiqotlarning ko'payishiga sabab bo'ladi va bu sabab o'laroq tadqiqotlar uchun maqolamiz dasturi amal bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль языковых явлений в передаче мысли в речь. Анализ языковых явлений можно изучать на кафедре синтаксической стилистики языкознания. Синтаксис занимается расположением слов, определением положения слов в беглости речи и формирует языковые явления для правильного построения предложений. Иногда возникает необходимость усиления речи, и в речи традиционно задействованы нормативные приемы. Примеры таких устройств известны и они систематизированы по определенным принципам. Именно в этом смысле в статье говорится о том, как языковые мероприятия и средства необходимы для обогащения нашей речи и беглого выражения наших мыслей. В статье упоминаются некоторые языковые явления и их классификация. Необходимость детального изучения языковых явлений на основе научно-теоретических источников сама по себе вызывает увеличение исследований по этой теме, а основой для этих исследований служит программа нашей статьи.

Key words: Detachment, inversion, parallelism, repetition, antithesis, ellipsis.

Kalit so'zlar: Ilova qurilmalar, inversiya, parallellik, takrorlash, antiteza, ellipsis.

Ключевые слова: Присоединение, инверсия, параллелизм, повторение, антитеза, многоточие.

Introduction

Syntax deals with the patterns of word arrangement and formulates roles for correct sentence building. Sometimes a need arises to intensify the utterance and the normative structures are replaced by what is traditionally called rhetorical figures, figures of speech or syntactical stylistic devices. Patterns of such devices are well-known and they are systematised according to some principles. For example, I.R Galperin singles out the following principles: 1) compositional patterns of syntactical arrangement, 2) peculiar linkage, 3) particular use of colloquial constructions, 4) stylistic use of structural meaning. Here is a table showing the distribution of syntactical intensifiers. The English language is characterised by such specific syntactical feature as fixed word order. Normative is the following word order in a sentence, presented symbolically Subject, Predicate,

Object, Modifier. Any shift from this word order results in some effect, and deviant structures can carry stylistic function. The English language is characterised by such specific syntactical feature as fixed word order. Normative is the following word order in a sentence, presented symbolically Subject, Predicate, Object, Modifier. Any shift from this word order results in some effect, and deviant structures can carry stylistic function.

Material extraction technology and research method

Inversion (stylistic) is a syntactical stylistic device in which the direct word order is changed either completely so that the predicate precedes the subject (complete inversion), or partially so that the object precedes the subject-predicate pair (partial inversion)

Not for a moment did I think I would be offered the job, so I was amazed when I got it.

Not till I got home did I realise my wallet was missing.

Detachment – a stylistic device based on singling out a secondary member of the sentence with the help of punctuation (intonation). *I bring your newspaper. Daily.* It is a stylistic device based on the author's desire to give a greater significance to a secondary member of the sentence, usually an attribute or an adverbial modifier. This member is detached from the rest of the sentence by means of such punctuation marks as commas, dashes or full stops. Being formally torn away from the word it syntactically depends on this particular element is closely related to it semantically. *She was come. For good.* Sometimes a detached construction may acquire the form of an explanatory or qualifying remark put into a sentence. Such variant of detachment is called parenthesis. In writing parenthesis is indicated by commas, brackets or dashes. *I know (if only I could forget it) that you cheated on her.* **Parenthesis** – a qualifying, explanatory or appositive word, phrase, clause, sentence, or other sequence which interrupts a syntactic construction without otherwise affecting it, having often a characteristic intonation and indicated in writing by commas, brackets or dashes.

The necessary condition in parallel constructions is identical or similar syntactical structure in two or more sentences or parts of a sentence in close succession. **Parallel construction** – reiteration of the structure of several sentences (clauses), and not of their lexical "flesh". Almost always includes some type of lexical repetition, and such a convergence produces a very strong effect, foregrounding at one go logical, rhythmic, emotive and expressive aspects of the utterance. *She likes cooking, jogging, and reading.* Chiasmus is also based on the repetition of syntactical patterns, but it has a reversed order in one of the two utterances. *She was a good sport about all this, but so was he.* Chiasmus is a syntactical, not a lexical device and one must differentiate it from parallel constructions or epigrams: 1) reversed parallelism of the structure of several sentences (clauses); 2) inversion of the first construction in the second part. If the first sentence (clause) has a direct word order - SPO, the second one will have it inverted - OPS. *So long as men can breathe or eyes can see. So long lives this and this gives life to thee.* (W.Shakespeare)

It is a stylistic device based on repeating words, word groups or sentences for some stylistic purposes: to draw the attention of the reader to the key-word of the utterance, to emphasise the main idea of the sentence. There are several formal varieties of repetition. Simple Repetition- no definite place in the sentence, the repeated unit occurs in various positions. The stylistic function is to emphasise both the logical and the emotional meaning of the reiterated word (phrase). *I really don't see anything romantic in proposing. It is very romantic to be in love. But there is nothing romantic about a definite proposal.* (O.Wilde) It is a repeated use of the same word or sentence one after the other. *He was the man in the Iron Mask. A grey metallic face with iron cheekbones and narrow iron brow, iron folds, hard and unchanging, ran perpendicularly down his cheeks, his nose was the iron beak of some thin delicate bird of ravine.* Anaphora - the beginning of two or more sentences (clauses) is repeated. The main stylistic function is not so much to emphasise the repeated unit as to create the background for the non-repeated unit, which, through its novelty, becomes foregrounded. The deliberate repetition of a word or phrase at the beginning of several successive clauses or paragraphs. **Epiphora** -- the end of successive sentences (clauses) is repeated. The main stylistic function is to add stress to the final words of the sentence. *I wake up and I'm alone and I walk round Warley and I'm alone; and I talk with people and I'm alone and I look at his face when I'm home and it's dead.* (J.Braine) **Framing** - the beginning of the sentence is repeated in the end, thus forming the "frame" for the non-repeated part of the sentence (utterance). The stylistic function is to elucidate the notion mentioned in the beginning of the sentence, to concretise and to specify its semantics. *Obviously - this is a streptococcal infection. Obviously.* (W.Deeping). The initial

elements are repeated at the end of an utterance or a paragraph. You've made a nice mess, you have. **Anadiplosis** -- the end of one clause (sentence) is repeated in the beginning of the following one. The stylistic function is to elucidate the notion, to concretise and to specify its semantics on a more modest level. *Now he understood. He understood many things. One can be a person first. A man first and then a black man or a white man.* (P. Abrahams). It is a repetition of the word or group of words that end one clause (or sentence) at the beginning of the next one. *She was ever so beautiful, more beautiful than "D", or "Mademoiselle", or "Auntie" June or even "Auntie Folly", to whom he had taken a fancy.* Chain repetition . . . a, a . . . b, b . . . several successive repetitions The effect is that of the smoothly developing logical reasoning. "To think better of it," returned the gallant Blandois, "would be to slight a lady, to slight a lady would be to be deficient in chivalry towards the sex, and chivalry towards the sex is a part of my character." (Ch. Dickens) Failure meant poverty, poverty meant squalor, squalor led, in the final stages, to the smells and stagnation of B. Inn Alley. (D. du Maurier) It is the succession of several anadiploses. *Rapidly the feeling became a strong hunch, the hunch became a conviction, and the conviction became a compulsion. He absolutely had to get home.* **Enumeration** - a stylistic device by which separate things, objects, phenomena, properties, actions are named one by one so that they produce a chain, the links of which, being syntactically in the same position (homogeneous parts of speech), are forced to display some kind of semantic homogeneity, remote through it may seem. Integrates both homogeneous and heterogeneous elements into one whole, unlike polysyndeton

The principal production of these towns ... appear to be soldiers, sailors, Jews, chalk, shrimps, officers and dock-yard men.

It is a stylistic device by which separate things, properties or actions are brought together forming a chain of grammatically and semantically homogeneous parts of an utterance. *She wasn't sure of anything anymore, of him, herself their friends, her work, their future.* **Suspense** -- a deliberate postponement of the completion of the sentence with the help of embedded clauses (homogeneous members) separating the predicate from the subject and introducing less important facts and details first, while the expected information of major importance is reserved till the end of the sentence (utterance) a compositional device which consists in arranging the matter of a communication in such a way that the less important, descriptive, subordinate parts are amassed at the beginning, the main idea being withheld till the end of the sentence. *Mankind, says a Chinese manuscript, which my friend M. was obliging enough to read and explain to me, for the first seventy thousand ages ate their meat raw.* (Ch. Lamb) Suspense (or retardation) is a stylistic device based on the author's desire to delay giving the reader (or listener) the most important information. In trying to do so he puts the less important, subordinate facts and details first withholding the main idea till the end of the sentence. *Two women who were hastening home to scramble their husbands' dinners together - it was five minutes to four - stopped to look at her.* The suspense in the sentence is organised by introducing a subordinate clause and a parenthetical remark between the subject and the predicate. The device of suspense is especially favoured by orators. Its function is to keep the reader/listener in a state of uncertainty and expectation. **Climax** - a semantically complicated parallel construction, in which each next word combination (clause, sentence) is logically more important or emotionally stronger and more explicit. Three types: logical climax, emotive climax, quantitative climax. *We were all in all to one another, it was the morning of life, it was bliss, it was frenzy, it was everything else of that sort in the highest degree.* (Ch. Dickens) *I am firm, thou art obstinate, he is pig-headed.* (B. Charlestone) *No tree, no shrub, no blade of grass that was not owned.* (J. Galsworthy) An arrangement of sentences (or of the homogeneous parts of one sentence) which secures a gradual increase in significance importance, or emotional tension in the utterance. An ascending series of words or utterances in which intensity and significance increase step by step. Depending on the nature of the phenomenon emphasised one can differentiate between three types of climax; logical, emotional and quantitative. In logical climax every consecutive word or utterance is more significant or essential than the preceding one from the logical point of view. Thus the objective or subjective author's attitude towards the thing is disclosed. In emotional climax consecutive words or utterances are more powerful from the emotional point of view. *She was a crashing, she was a stupendous, she was an excruciating bore.* Quantitative climax is based on the intensification of quantity in each consecutive word, word group or utterance. *Mary had counted the months, the weeks, the days, the hours to Antony's return.*

Anticlimax - a climax suddenly interrupted by an unexpected turn of the thought which defeats expectations of the reader (listener) and ends in complete semantic reversal of the emphasised idea. *It was appalling - and soon forgotten.* (J.Galsworthy). In order to stress certain qualities of the thing described it may be necessary to set it against another thing possessing contrasting features. **Antithesis** is a balanced two-step structure in which the antagonistic objects or ideas are presented by dictionary or contextual antonyms, as in: For many are called but few are chosen. In the case of developed antithesis we deal with semantically opposed statements or pictures. *It was very sad in the street, Jake holding the box of oranges, and him walking beside Jake telling him to smile big, and the sky was sad, and there were no leaves on the trees, and the street was sad, and it was very funny, the smell of the oranges was clean and good and they looked so nice it was very funny. The oranges looked so nice and they were so sad.* One should differentiate antithesis, which is a stylistically coloured opposition, from a literary device termed contrast. The latter is based on logical opposition and adds nothing to the meaning of an utterance. The current study presupposes allusion as the most frequent verbal marker of intertextuality. In the light of the theory of intertextuality, allusion accomplishes function of "intertext" and considered as a reference to the precedent text decoding of which requires establishing actual connections with the precedent text and recipient text. It is necessary to state at the beginning that the term "allusion" appears in many European languages in the XVI century. But, despite the long tradition of using the term in literature and linguistics, the phenomenon begins to be actively studied only at the end of XX century. Thus, to date there has been a scarcity of theoretical and practical work that adequately addresses the comparative work of allusion in literary and precedent text. Therefore, here the attempt is made to scrutinize broadly definitions of allusion, functions, effects, types, and semantic-stylistic aspects of allusions with practical implications.

In fact, literary work can be implicit because of the associations evoked by allusion. Several definitions of allusion have been set forth in recent literary studies. In an effort to clarify and define literary allusion, the most commonly cited and utilized definitions will now be examined:

1. an indirect reference, by word or phrase, to a historical, political, literary, mythological fact or to a fact of everyday life made in the course of speaking or writing. The use of allusion presupposes the background knowledge of the event, thing, or person alluded to on the part of reader or listener" moreover, allusion should be regarded as "a vessel into which new meaning is poured".

2. a device for the simultaneous activation of two texts. The simultaneous activation of the two texts results in the formation of intertextual patterns whose nature cannot be predetermined

3. a sign or marker that calls to the reader's mind another known text for a specific purpose

4. a tip of the iceberg which means the entire semantic system is compressed into a single word

5. a linguocultural unit or linguocultureme, since it is imbued with cultural information reflecting its historical, religious, mythological, and literary aspects

Comprehensive studies demonstrate that allusion has complex nature and can be considered complex phenomenon, concerning its interpretation is to be connected with extralinguistic factors, such as surrounding, culture, educational level and etc. We can assume that allusion establishes a link between a text and the history and society in which the allusion is generated. As it can be seen allusion is meaningful only in the culture or subculture in which they originate and may convey nothing in other cultures.

Assessment –characterizing; Allusion fulfills assessment –characterizing function when it is utilized to assess and characterize situation, event, and character. For illustrative purposes, let's analyze the following extract: "...Aunt Alexandra would have been analogous to Mount Everest: throughout my early life, she was cold and there" (Harper Lee, "To Kill a Mockingbird"). In this example, the use of allusion brings back a flow of associations that are built up online to integrate information from different frames that activate intertextual competence and precedent knowledge of the reader. To be specific, the analysis of the frame, associative and contextual links as well as knowledge structure of "Mount Everest" makes it possible to point out the following conceptual features: greatness, power, superiority, on the one hand, and the unavailability of mystery, on the other. **Occasional**- allusion performs occasional functions when the references are used to historical facts and personalities, recreating the spirit of the age in the work. Here we can recall a well-known novel by John Steinbeck "Grapes of Wrath" where the action takes place against the backdrop of the ecological

disaster the Dust Bowl and the historical event the Great Depression of the 1930s in the United States. In his work there is a set of realities associated with this historical event.

"Great Depression caused a long period of draught and desperate plight...In 1931,dust from the seriously over-plowed and over-grazed prairie lands began to blow. And, it continued to blow for eight long, dry years..." **Textstructuring**-allusion discloses certain themes uniting all parts of the information integrity. The best extract can be analyzed from, John Steinbeck's "The grapes of wrath", novel: "I been in the hills, thinking almost you (Jim Casy) might say like Jesus when into the wilderness to think His way out of troubles". Jim Casy, known as the Christ figure of the novel, devotes much of his time fighting against the injustice likewise devoted figure Jesus Christ. Casy even holds a hidden clue in his name; the initials of Jim Casy are the same as those of Jesus Christ. Here, the decoding of conceptual peculiarities of allusion is a partial match between input mental spaces into a "blended" mental space. By now, it is obvious that interpreting conceptual features of allusion is based on extensive empirical observation in multiple areas of meaning construction. Through, incorporating allusion we can effectively and economically include certain feelings and situations creating symbolic picture in the reader's perception. Talking about the allusion, it is vital to analyze the types of it. The scholars outlined the following wide-spread types of allusion. **Religious allusion**-the religious precedent texts are books such as Bible and Qur'an that are brought down through the years and passed down from generations. These culturally and cognitively known precedent texts have many common allusions which are used in the literary works. Allusion in this type is often used to summarize broad, complex ideas or emotions in one quick, powerful image This might be used in the form of: a) quotations from the religious scriptures with explicit or implicit references; b) proper names associated with religious spheres As for the latter form we might allude to Noah, who had no faults and was the only good man of his time, to express righteousness . Furthermore, the idea of fatherhood love can be well understood by alluding to Abraham. Cain is an excellent example to convey banishment, rejection, or evil, for he was rejected of his homeland by God . Thus, allusions serve an important function in writing as they allow the reader to understand a difficult concept by relating to an "etalon" name, event or situation. Mostly, for the positive characteristic of hero the author uses biblical anthroponomy allusions. There are many such references commonly used by a number of writers when they want their readers to understand the deep and implicit meanings enhancing emotive expressivity pragmatic effect as well. **Mythological allusions** are references established directly or indirectly to some myth, i.e fabulous stories about world creation and destruction, gods and heroes, their deeds, victories, and defeats [4.111]. It plays a huge role in obtaining the bright and sensational information. One of the most important functions of myth is to establish behavioural model. Each time mythological allusion is used, it has a moral interpretation. The various allusions are derived from different mythologies like Greek, Roman, and Norse. **Historical allusion** is the next extensively used type of allusion. This connects with the historical event or figures. Such allusions are very easy for decoding as they are concrete and precise but at the same time this is the reason that they are less emotional and expressive. An allusion referring to literature is known as a literary allusion. The usage of such allusions is understandable by a literary and culturally component reader. By explicitly or implicitly referring to other literary text, the authors suppose that many readers know these writers and their works rather well. A nice example to illustrate the associative links between the precedent and recipient texts, can be the extract from the novel "Letters from prison" by J.Dennis that is alluding to well-known novel "The last of the Mohicans" by James Cooper: I just completed (Lincoln) Steffen's autobiography. All in all, quite interesting... 'tis a book worth reading, a rich and colorful story of one of the "last Mohicans", a real progressive, a genuine liberal. Allusion-metaphor is based on the associative mechanism. Even, some linguists (E.N. Kovalnko, M.I. Kiose) consider allusion as a variety of metaphor. However, unlike metaphor, in understanding allusion addressee is supposed to decode allusion and to know precedent text that has cultural peculiar features of the nation. In this regard, to illustrate an example of allusion-metaphor, we can analyze the extract from Somerset Maugham's novel "The Moon and Sixpence" "if in the loneliness of his studio he (Strickland) wrestled with the Angel of the Lord he never allowed a soul to divine his anguish" . **Pastiche**- related to the Italian word for 'paste,' this is a collage of words, phrases, or entire passages from one or more other authors that creates a new literary work. The more elaborate pastiche will usually incorporate elements of plot, theme, style, and even character development. The **Metamorphoses** by the Roman poet Ovid is actually a giant pastiche of hundreds of earlier Greco-Roman myths! **Parody**- very

similar in form to the pastiche, the parody re-appropriates the work of others, but for the purpose of poking fun rather than praising. Many of 'Weird' Al Yankovic's songs are parodies of the work of other popular artists.[75] Although the subtitle has been dropped from most modern editions, the allusive qualities Frankenstein; or, the Modern Prometheus, is a the horror novel by Mary Shelley, still remain. The reference here to the Titan Prometheus relies on centuries of interpretation through Greek myth and drama.

Direct intertextual relationships can be explicit or implied and may include a variety of literary devices (e.g., allusion, metonymy, synecdoche) or represent examples of anagram, adaptation, translation, parody, pastiche, imitation, and other kinds of transformation. Gerard Genette proposed the term 'transtextuality' as a more inclusive term than "intertextuality" He listed five subtypes: -- intertextuality: quotation, plagiarism, allusion; -- paratextuality: the relation between a text and its 'paratext' - that which surrounds the main body of the text - such as titles, headings, prefaces, epigraphs, dedications, acknowledgements, footnotes, illustrations, dust jackets, etc.; -- architextuality: designation of a text as part of a genre or genres (Genette refers to designation by the text itself, but this could also be applied to its framing by readers); - metatextuality: explicit or implicit critical commentary of one text on another text; -- hypertextuality: the relation between a text and a preceding 'hypotext' - a text or genre on which it is based but which it transforms, modifies, elaborates or extends (including parody, spoof, sequel, translation).

Conclusion

In my opinion, we can define 'text analysis' as the systematic dissection of a textual unity in its constituent parts and the study of those parts in relation to each other. By consequence, text analysis focuses on the linguistic elements present in the text. Texts may be analyzed with different aims and from several perspectives. A first text-analytic research goal is of a theoretical nature. It concerns the further development of linguistic theory at the text level: how are texts structured? There are now several well-established theories that propose mechanisms by which the meaning of individual sentences can be constructed, but the situation with entire texts is different. Text analysis is of crucial importance to the further development of text linguistics. A second aim is to provide insight into the cognitive processes of reading and writing, or in the text representation that language users have of a text. In reading research, the role of text structure is an important research topic in which text analyses are used to model both the text structure and the representation that readers make of it. A third aim is of a computational linguistic nature: the development of computational models of automatic summarization, text generation, and interpretation. Here, the analysis of natural texts should provide the rule system to arrive at such computational models. Although some theories and models discussed in the sections to follow were explicitly developed in the context of such a computational enterprise computational text analyses are not discussed here. A fourth aim is the evaluation of text quality in the context of written composition and document design. A text analysis can provide the basis for a comparison of similar texts, enabling researchers to compare the writing ability of the authors. In document design, text analysis can predict areas where readers may have difficulties. Cognitive Stylistics deals with the cognitive processes which occur during the act of reading and influence text interpretation. It takes into account both the formal features of language and the nonlinguistic context of the readers in constructing meaning out of a text, therefore veering away from "impressionistic reading and imprecise intuition". Since readers are active constructors of meaning carrying different backgrounds and context, cognitive stylistics claims that it is impossible to find the meaning of the text. The following are some theories and analytical frameworks commonly used in cognitive stylistic analysis. Schema Theory describes the process of how we incorporate our world knowledge to the interpretation of texts through the process of defamiliarization, or the restructuring of existing schemas to create a new perspective of the world.

Foregrounding -theory explains the readers' ability to use prior knowledge infacilitating recognition of spatial foregrounding through parallelism and deviation and identifying the parts of the text which should be given attention. Cognitive Metaphor Theory states that thought processes, and not just language, are metaphorical and that our schematic knowledge contributes to how we construct new perspectives of ourselves, our lives and our world. Metaphor used in language merely manifests how the mind operates, reflecting the metaphors in one's conceptual system. Blending Theory establishes the idea that meaning is a result of blending elements from various input sources. Cognitive Stylistic Analysis of a Literary Text will analyze

since it deals with figurative language, particularly metaphor, which students find hard to comprehend in a literary text.

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